

1 **TLR13, a murine-specific TLR.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We describe here properties of the mammalian and murine-specific toll-like receptor TLR13. TLR13
7 expression was silenced by the gram negative bacteria *N. gonorrhoea* in bone marrow derived
8 macrophages and following exposure to the TNF superfamily ligand RANKL. TLR13 was expressed in a
9 stage-specific manner in the murine hematopoietic compartment, activated over the course of
10 differentiation in a HOXA9-OHT inducible bone marrow system. In a dextran sodium sulfate (DSS) colitis
11 model, TLR13 expression was inflammation-responsive as evidenced by activation in the gastrointestinal
12 tract.

13 **References**

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